

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: DUBE****FIRST NAME: OLIVER****PROGRAM CODE : DSDD****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: RP 6 (QUIZ)****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes).

The author did use Zotero to insert references.

The author used the following software: MSOffice ProPlus

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. **The two Chicago styles of source citation are...**

- Notes-bibliography format and author date formats¹.**
- Notes-bibliography and author publisher formats.
- Endnotes and author year format.
- Footnotes for Bibliography and Endnotes for authors.

2. **The four main reasons for citation are given as follows:**

- Giving credit to the publisher; providing assurance to readers of the accuracy of the work; set the work within a contextual framework; assisting readers extend your research or follow it up.
- Giving credit to the originator; providing assurance to readers of the accuracy of the work; set the work within a contextual**

¹ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for students and researchers* (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press), 25.

- framework; and assisting readers extend your research or follow it up².**
- Giving credit to the writer; providing assurance to readers of the intellectual property; set the work within a contextual framework; assisting readers extend your research or follow it up.
 - Giving depth of research work; setting scene for further research; set the work within a contextual framework; assisting readers credit your work.
3. **A claim must be supported with reason and evidence: Is there a difference between the two terms?**
- Reason must be from authoritative sources whereas evidence originate from common knowledge.
 - Reason is an abstract based on one's thought pattern whereas evidence come from outside ones' mind hence require citation³.**
 - A reason is an abstract whereas evidence is a logical thought pattern.
 - The terms mean the same and can used interchangeably.

² Ibid, 161.

³ Ibid, 38.

⁴ Ibid, 129.

4. **The typical order of elements and punctuation in a reference list entry for a book is follows...**
- Author's last Name, Author's First Name. Year of Publication. Title of Book. Place of Publication: Publisher Name⁴.**
 - Author. Date of Publication. Title. Publisher. Place of publication.
 - Author's first name and Last. Title. Publisher place and publisher. Year of Publication.
 - Originator. Year of edition. Title. Publisher. Country of publication.
5. **The difference between a colon and a semi colon is depict as characterized by the following;**
- These work the same and hence can be used interchangeably.
 - A colon introduces a sentence whereas the semi colon allows several phrases to be introduced.
 - They have the same function as a comma or period.
 - A colon introduces a phrase whereas a semi colon is stronger than a comma and marks a great break in the continuity of a sentence⁵.**
6. **The philosophical principles that shape the logic of inquiry can be broken down into four aspects.**

5. Ibid, 176.

6.Linda D. Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End* (Los Angeles: Sage Publications), 10.

- 1.Epistemology 2. Ontology 3. Physiology 4. Methodology.
- 1.Epistemology 2. Ontology 3. Action Research 4. Methodology.
- 1.Epistemology 2. Ontology 3. Axiology 4. Methodology⁶.**
- 1.Action research 2. Experimental Research 3. Epistemology 4. Methodology.

7. **The main emphasis and focus of qualitative research are that:**

- Exploration, discovery, and description of phenomenon with intention of understanding the social setting to enable transferable knowledge⁷.**
- Explanation, discovery, and description of phenomenon with intention of understanding the social setting to enable transferable knowledge.
- Explanation, exploration, and description of phenomenon with intention of understanding the cause effect relationship.
- Description of phenomenon with intention of explaining the origin of social knowledge.

8. **The adoption of the British English by the European Union is based on the following main reason.**

7. Ibid, 11.

8. European Commission, *English Style Guide: A handbook for authors and translators in the European Commission. Directorate-General for Translation*, (Brussel: European Commission Press 2011), 1.

- The English Language provided key features of the union's communication tools.
 - The English Language was unique and was to make it easier to trade with USA.
 - The English language was found to be easier to learn than other European languages.
 - Language is key in enhancing the organization identity, uniqueness and enhancing effective communication⁸.**
9. **The establishment of structure and operation of the European Union is enshrined in which agreement?**
- The treaties of Amsterdam and now it stands as a legal entity.
 - The Treaty of Lisbon and it now stands as legal entity⁹.**
 - The treaty of Nice and Rome which established a constitution.
 - The treaty of Madrid ratified in Lisbon.
10. **In assessing a research project, the matrix of finding through to recommendation must be applied which consists of the following:**
- If/ Then/ Therefore /Thus¹⁰.**
 - If/What/ Therefore/Thus.
 - What/ How/ Therefore/ Thus.
 - What/How/ Where/ Therefore.
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9. Ibid, 54.

10. Linda D. Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, 31.

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